

Pencils made resource efficiently in Europe

The company uses bio composite material to produce pencils and crayons from a single cast: three granulates - one each for the surface, the body and the lead of the pencil - are produced in a one step process. This can be achieved by binding and recycling spruce fibres with a polymer matrix material and a special developed co-extrusion process which joins all pencil materials. Conventional manufacturing methods for pencils and crayons take up to 30 process steps and pencils are often made from non-European wood. The company started selling WOPEX-based pencils in 2009.

Today steadily growing share of the company's pencils and crayons are made from this material. This process is still revolutionising pencil manufacturing in terms of production time, costs and new opportunities for innovative products.

Image: Staedtler

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Utilisation of high percentages of side-stream material from woodworking industry enables a further stage of re-use and cascading and as a result small parts from the tree can be used in the pencil industry.
- ▶ Spruce side streams are upcycled into pencils presenting a functional use of material side streams adding value to the product.
- ▶ The innovative production process eliminates waste that would be generated by traditional woodworking.
- ▶ The use of energy and emissions from the production process is minimised through optimised processing that reduces the number of usual multi-production steps.
- ▶ The modern manufacturing process makes this pencil particularly robust, which can be seen in the high break resistance of the lead.
- ▶ Pencils with better usability than the traditional pencils are products that can attract wide consumer acceptance enhancing consumer attention to bio-composite materials.

Regional coverage and transferability

So far, this good practice is mainly traced to the Central European region, where pencil producers have implemented biocomposite materials to replace virgin wood. The granules that are used for the pencil production are a basic material for different applications beyond the writing instrument industry and it has been tested in other products as well. This allows to predict a high transferability to other consumer products to be produced across Europe.

